

Innate Virtual Analgesia

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Abstract

Computerised virtual manipulation of virtual images of one's own pained body parts is known to produce significant pain reduction. However, using a modified sensitivity retraining therapy for hand heat and pressure sensing produced a higher-order sensory connection to a stimulated innate virtual (or 'phantom') invisible body outline illusion perceivable by a co-stimulated tactile illusionary sense of virtual touch providing interoceptive feedback. Operations on the partly dissociated body image using the stimulated virtual touch sense provided self-reported therapeutic ontelagent gain of function: one-shot persistent innate analgesia for knee arthritis, nausea, jaw pain, headache and musculoskeletal pain, and multishot for pelvic inflammation and others.

Keywords:

Innate analgesia, nociception control, illusion-mediated analgesia, phantom body illusion, tactile illusion, ontelagence, gain of function, pain self-management.

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